

Energy Balance of Solar Water Heater

Multi-Apartment Residential Buildings in Tel Aviv

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Abstract

This work introduces a methodology for energy balance of solar water heaters (SWH). It describes the Israeli system for determination of the size of SWH, and calculations of the amount of energy gained by the SWH every month. It analyzes the central forced circulation system for the upper 9 floors of a residential building in Tel Aviv.

The balance is for the demand scenario as determined using national statistics (unique to Israel). Electrical backup is 12% of the energy supplied by solar collectors.

The balance shows that the energy consumption of hot water actually used is 57% of the total energy, and energy losses are 30%. 13% of the energy is not used as in summer SWH supplies more hot water than required.

This work may be useful for a techno-economic evaluation of water heating options and calculations of optimal solutions. It also contains a large volume of useful data and information and can serve as a solar water heating manual or basic material for solar energy study.

1. Glossary

E	energy [kcal] (not kcal/hr)
EE	excessive energy, solar energy not used
Ein	total energy input
ELb	energy consumption for electric backup
ELp	electricity consumption of circulation pump for one apartment
Emix	energy loss caused by the mixed layer of the hot water by the cold water entering the storage tank, resulting in mixed water temperature below the temperature that can be used for a shower (below 37°C)
Eout	total energy output
Est	energy stored in storage tank [kcal]
EstB	energy stored in storage tank including backup [kcal]
EstU	useful energy stored in storage tank, Est reduced by Emix [kcal]
EU	useful energy, the energy of hot water actually used in showers
kcal	kilo-calorie, energy unit
kWh	kilo-Watt-hour, energy unit
M	thermal mass energy losses
Mc	energy losses in the thermal mass of circulation pipes after the end of circulation
McB	energy losses in the thermal mass of the main circulation pipes between floors inside the building, after the end of circulation
McR	energy losses in the thermal mass of the main circulation pipes on the roof, after the end of circulation
McSt	energy losses in the thermal mass of circulation pipes from the main pipes between the floors to the storage tank, after the end of circulation
Ms	energy losses in the thermal mass of the hot water supply pipe
MT	total thermal mass losses [kWh/month]
Q	energy in time [kcal/hr] (not kcal)
r	thermal resistance of material [kcal/hr,°C]

r_{in}, r_{out}	thermal resistance of laminar layer [kcal/m ² ,hr,°C]
SE	solar energy leaving collectors for a single apartment
SWH	Solar Water Heater
T _a	ambient air temperature 24 hours, month average based on typical year [7] [°C]
T _b	temperature inside the building [°C]
T _c	cold water (city water) temperature supplied to the storage tank of the SWH [°C]
T _{st}	storage tank water average temperature [°C]
T _{stB}	storage tank water average temperature including backup [°C]
T _{sun}	ambient air temperature month average in sun hours only [°C]
U	overall heat transfer coefficient [kcal/m ² ,hr,°C]
V	water flow [liter/hour]
X	heat exchange losses
X _c	heat exchange losses of circulation pipes
X _{cR}	heat exchange losses of the main circulation pipes on roof
X _{cB}	heat exchange losses of the main circulation pipes between floors inside the building
X _{cSt}	heat exchange losses of circulation pipes to each storage tank
XLPE	cross-linked Poly-Ethylene
X _s	heat exchange losses of hot water supply pipe between the storage tank and the shower
X _{st}	heat exchange losses of storage tank
X _T	total heat exchange losses
α	thermal conductivity of laminar layer [kcal/m ² ,hr,°C]
λ	specific thermal conductivity [kcal/m,hr,°C]
ρ	density [kg/liter]

2. Introduction

Solar water heaters (SWH) must be installed in new buildings in Israel according to the law. Solar water heaters save 5 % of the national electricity consumption [1] and are an important component of the Israeli economy and standard of living. Solar legislation in Israel requires installation of solar water heaters in 9 upper floors of new residential buildings according to the national standards.

This work aims to develop a methodology for the energy balance of SWH, including calculations of the amount of energy gained by the SWH every month and the energy losses in circulation pipes, hot water supply pipe, storage tank, and the solar collector.

It analyzes the central forced circulation system for the upper 9 floors of the residential building in Tel Aviv as required by the law in Israel. The balance is for the demand scenario as determined using national statistics (unique to Israel).

All conditions are for Israel so the results do not necessarily apply to other countries.

3. Energy Units

This work is in Metric Units. Usually metric units apply Joule as energy unit. In this work the energy unit is kilocalorie, the energy required to heat 1 kg of water (1 liter) by 1°C. 1 kcal is equal to 4,186.8 Joule, and 1 kJ is equal to 0.23885 kcal.

Application of kcal instead of Joule is very convenient for works involving water heating, as the temperature difference immediately indicates the amount of energy in kcal.

Thermal energy is also expressed in some tables in kWh, kilo-Watt-hour (thermal)

Electric energy is expressed in kWh or kWh kilo-Watt-hour (electric).

1 kWh is 859.85 kcal and 1 kcal is 1.1630 Wh.

4. Solar Water Heater

The solar water heating system selected for this work is Chromagen [6] and consists of the following main parts:

- central collectors array
- individual 150 liters vertical storage tanks with inside 2.5kW instant backup
- circulation pump
- circulation pipes
- hot water supply pipe

According to the law, the tilt angle for central solar installations in residential buildings in Israel is 45° [1].

Location: Tel Aviv / Israel 32.0929° N, 34.8072° E

5. Selected Solar Collector

The selected solar collector for this work is Chromagen F (CR120) 16mm selective paint [6].

Table 1 - Selected solar collector [6]

Standard capacity [1] [kcal/day]	7,110
Risers diameter [mm]	16
Gross area [m ²]	2.77
Aperture area [m ²]	2.56
Length [m]	2.18
Width [m]	1.27
Weight [kg]	43
Fluid capacity [L]	4.13
Thermal mass, MC [kcal/°C]	9.88
Absorptance, α	0.90
Emissivity, ε	0.45
Linear efficiency coefficient a	-4.80
Linear efficiency coefficient b	0.72
Standard efficiency [1]	63.1%
Stagnation temperature [°C]	170

Collector's efficiency depends on its temperature, ambient temperature, and solar radiation. In this work, the collector standard efficiency of 63.1% is regarded as average efficiency and applied to all months.

As the solar energy data are for 1 m², also the collector data will be for 1 m² of its net opening.

Table 2 - Collector thermal mass, MC [6]

		Collector /m ²	
Opening	m ²	2.56	1.00
Weight	kg	43	16.80
Weight Cu	kg		8.40
Weight Al	kg		5.04
Weight Steel	kg		3.36
Weight Water	kg	4.1	1.60
c CU	kcal/kg°C		0.09
c Al	kcal/kg°C		0.21
c Steel	kcal/kg°C		0.12
mc Cu	kcal/°C,m ²		0.77
mc Al	kcal/°C,m ²		1.08
mc Steel	kcal/°C,m ²		0.40
mc Water	kcal/°C,m ²		1.60
Thermal Mass, MC	kcal/°C	9.88	3.86

Table 3 - Solar collector size

Collector size according to the law	41	kcal/day,Liter
Storage tank in each apartment	150	Liter
Collector size for each apartment	6,150	kcal/day
Collector's standard efficiency	63.1%	
Standard solar radiation	4,400	kcal/m ² ,day
Collector size for each apartment	2.21	m ²

Collector size	7,110	kcal/day
Collector size	2.56	m ²
Collector size	0.00036	m ² /kcal/d
Collector size for each apartment	6,150	kcal/day
Collector size for each apartment	2.21	m ²

6. Solar Radiation

Solar radiation data on the horizontal surface for a typical year in Tel Aviv is from [7].

Solar radiation data in a typical year on a tilt angle of 45° in Tel Aviv is from [8].

Chart 1 - Solar radiation in a typical year in Tel Aviv on tilt angle 45°, W/m² [8]

Table 4 - Solar radiation in Tel Aviv in a typical year on tilt angle 45°

	kWh/m ² ,day	kWh/m ² ,month	kcal/m ² ,day	kcal/m ² ,month
January	4.05	125	3,479	107,861
February	4.50	126	3,870	108,374
March	5.37	167	4,619	143,181
April	5.54	166	4,766	142,980
May	5.94	184	5,110	158,402
June	6.27	188	5,388	161,647
July	5.98	186	5,146	159,524
August	6.12	190	5,266	163,253
September	5.80	174	4,988	149,639
October	5.08	157	4,366	135,359
November	4.86	146	4,183	125,477
December	4.02	125	3,455	107,120
Σ		1,934		1,662,816
Ave	5.30		4,553	
Min	4.02		3,455	
Max	6.27		5,388	

Calculations of solar collector energy output (SE) involve a uniform collector's standard efficiency of 63.1%.

Most of the year the solar radiation in Israel is higher than the standard radiation used for the determination of the collector's efficiency, which means that most of the year the collector is more efficient than tested. In this work, changes in the collector's efficiency will be neglected contributing to the conservativeness of the calculations.

The size of the solar collectors for a single apartment (A) is 2.21 m² and the solar collectors' standard efficiency is (η) 63.1%.

Solar energy leaving the collectors array for a single apartment is SE.

$$\mathbf{SE = Solar\ Radiation\ [kcal/m^2] * A\ [m^2] * \eta}$$

Table 5 - Solar energy leaving the collectors array for a single apartment, SE, kcal/hr

hr -->	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19
January	0	0	23	197	418	575	726	778	794	637	419	245	50	2	0
February	0	0	27	234	541	606	677	708	751	754	434	451	216	11	0
March	0	14	89	270	497	682	820	940	940	843	671	444	208	40	0
April	0	63	183	375	591	777	901	919	944	712	570	382	189	53	3
May	37	136	284	475	671	817	898	930	888	760	582	378	182	90	14
June	42	112	267	435	626	800	917	967	936	838	668	490	276	131	28
July	25	109	206	347	500	752	884	940	931	853	703	509	294	112	28
August	0	77	160	351	607	791	920	1029	939	903	720	498	256	97	12
September	0	76	217	480	701	728	835	1065	864	894	569	322	191	28	1
October	0	58	212	416	817	857	774	753	843	628	382	263	98	3	0
November	0	0	203	471	673	807	877	869	789	620	388	136	12	0	0
December	0	0	50	163	456	655	768	722	707	437	653	202	15	0	0

Table 6 - Solar energy leaving the collectors array for a single apartment, SE

	kcal/day	kcal/month	kWh/day	kWh/month
January	4,863	150,760	5.66	175
February	5,410	151,477	6.29	176
March	6,456	200,128	7.51	233
April	6,662	199,847	7.75	232
May	7,142	221,402	8.31	257
June	7,531	225,939	8.76	263
July	7,193	222,970	8.36	259
August	7,361	228,183	8.56	265
September	6,972	209,155	8.11	243
October	6,103	189,195	7.10	220
November	5,846	175,383	6.80	204
December	4,830	149,724	5.62	174
Σ		2,324,164		2,703
Ave	6,364		7.40	
Min	4,830		5.62	
Max	7,531		8.76	

7. Ambient Air Temperature

Chart 2 - Ambient air temperature in typical year in Tel Aviv, °C [7]

7.1. Cold Water Supply Temperature, T_c

Estimation of the city water (cold water) temperature (T_c) is based on 24 hours month average ambient temperature adding 3°C when the temperature is below 20°C.

7.2. Building Temperature for Hot Water Supply Pipe Between Floors, T_b

Building temperature will be regarded as 4°C above the average air temperature (T_b=T_a+4°C). Usually the pipe shaft in the building is not vented which increases the outside temperature of the pipe and decreases energy losses, however, this is not considered in this work contributing to the conservativeness of the calculation.

7.3. Initial Temperature

In this work, the initial temperature of the SWH is the ambient air temperature at sunrise.

The remaining heat from the previous day, and night cooling, are not considered.

Table 7 - Sunrise, sunset, and average temperatures

	T _a °C	T _c °C	Sunrise	Sunset	Sun hours hr/day	T _{sun} °C	T _b °C
January	12.1	15.1	6:41	16:58	10.3	14.2	16.1
February	12.7	15.7	6:23	17:26	11.1	14.8	16.7
March	14.2	17.2	5:51	17:48	12.0	16.0	18.2
April	18.0	20.0	5:12	18:10	13.0	19.9	22.0
May	20.0	20.0	4:43	18:31	13.8	21.5	24.0
June	23.4	23.4	4:34	18:49	14.3	24.9	27.4
July	25.1	25.1	4:45	18:48	14.1	26.6	29.1
August	25.5	25.5	5:05	18:25	13.3	27.5	29.5
September	24.6	24.6	5:24	17:47	12.4	26.7	28.6
October	21.8	21.8	5:44	17:08	11.4	23.7	25.8
November	16.5	19.5	6:09	16:41	10.5	18.9	20.5
December	13.1	16.1	6:33	16:37	10.1	15.5	17.1
Ave	18.9	20.3				20.8	22.9

T_a ambient air temperature 24 hours month average based on typical year [7]

T_{sun} ambient air temperature in sun hours only

T_c cold water (city water) temperature supplied to the storage tank of the SWH

T_b temperature inside the building

8. Thermal Mass Energy

The calculation of energy losses in thermal mass is based on the definition of specific heat:

$$c = E / (m * \Delta t)$$

E	energy [kcal]
m	mass [kg]
c	specific heat (at constant pressure) [kcal/kg,°C]
Δt	temperature rise caused by energy E [°C]

The following formula is frequently used in this work:

Formula 1 - Energy required to heat mass

$$\mathbf{E = m * c * \Delta t}$$

$$\mathbf{MC = m * c}$$

$$\mathbf{E = \Delta t * MC}$$

MC thermal mass [kcal/°C]

9. Circulation Pipes Diameter

Usually circulation pipes serve 9 floors of 2 sides of the residential building, 18 apartments. According to [9] the required water flow is 2 liters/minute per apartment. Considering the flow of 1m/s, the pipe diameter should be at least 46 mm.

Table 8 - Circulation pipes diameter

Flow per apartment	2	Liter/minute
Flow per 18 apartments	36	Liter/minute
Flow per 18 apartments	0.036	m3/minute
flow speed	1	meter/minute
Cross-section of the pipe	0.036	m2
Inside diameter	0.046	m
Inside diameter	46	mm
Standard steel pipe		
Outside diameter	60.3	mm
Thickness	3.9	mm
Inside diameter	52.5	mm

10. Circulation Pipes Length

Circulation pipe connecting solar collectors on the roof is 2.5 meters per apartment in one direction, 5 meters per apartment in both directions. For 18 apartments the total length of the circulation pipes on the roof will be at least 90 meters. 10 meters of the pipe length on the roof should be added to connect the collectors array with the risers between the floors in both directions.

The pipe length between floors is 27 meters in each direction, 54 meters in both directions.

The plastic pipe connecting the risers between the floors with the storage tank is 16 mm OD, 2 mm thick, 3 meters long in each direction, 6 meters per apartment.

11. Thermal Conductivity and Resistance of Laminar Layers

Laminar layers related to energy losses of SWH:

- Storage tank
 - inside: water laminar flow
 - outside: air laminar flow
- Circulation pipes on roof
 - inside: water turbulent flow

- outside: air turbulent flow
- Circulation pipes between floors
 - inside: water turbulent flow
 - outside: air laminar flow
- Hot water supply pipes
 - inside: water turbulent flow
 - outside: air laminar flow

Table 9 - Thermal conductivity and resistance of laminar layers

	α_{in} water	α_{out} air	r_{in} water	r_{out} air
	kcal/m ² °C,hr	kcal/m ² °C,hr	m ² °C,hr/kcal	m ² °C,hr/kcal
Storage tank	1,000	6.61	0.0010	0.1512
Circulation pipes located inside	5,000	6.61	0.0002	0.1512
Circulation pipes located outside	5,000	21.50	0.0002	0.0465
Hot water supply pipes	10,000	6.61	0.0001	0.1512

12. Heat Transfer

Energy losses of SWH involve 3 processes of heat transfer:

- conduction
- radiation
- convection

Energy loss calculations in this work involve conduction only, while radiation and convection are neglected.

Heat transfer by conduction is determined by Fourier's Law.

Formula 2 - Heat transfer by conduction

$$Q = U * A * \Delta t$$

- Q heat transfer [kcal/hr]
- U overall heat transfer coefficient [kcal/m²,hr,°C]
- A layer's area [m²]

Δt temperature difference on the both sides of the layer [°C]

The formula for heat transfer in multi-layer pipes and cylinders was developed in publication [5].

Formula 3 - Heat transfer in multi-layer pipe

$$Q = (\pi * L * \Delta t) / \{ [1 / (\alpha_{in} * d_{in1})] + [LN(d_{out1}/d_{in1}) / (2 * \lambda_1)] + [LN(d_{out2}/d_{in2}) / (2 * \lambda_2)] + [1 / (\alpha_{out} * d_{out2})] \}$$

L length of pipe/cylinder [meters]

α_{in} thermal conductivity of laminar layer inside the pipe, water side [kcal/m²,hr,°C]

α_{out} thermal conductivity the laminar layer outside the insulation of the pipe, air side [kcal/m²,hr,°C]

d_{in} inside diameter of the pipe [meters]

d_{out} outside diameter of the pipe [meters]

LN natural logarithm, logarithm to base e, in Excel: LN()

λ thermal conductivity of the layer [kcal/m°C,hr]

index 1 is related to the pipe/cylinder material

index 2 is related to the pipe's insulation

13. Heat Exchange in Storage Tank

13.1. Storage Tank Dimensions

The following dimensions are for Chromagen vertical storage tank 150 liters for SWH [5].

H out	1,021 mm
Dia out	565 mm
Insulation	40 mm
Inner tank thickness	3 mm
Sleeve	150 x 100 mm, 3 mm thick

Table 10 - Storage tank thermal mass

Volume	150	liter
Weight	54	kg
c Steel	0.12	kcal/kg°C
MC steel	6.48	kcal/°C
MC water	150	kcal/°C
MC total	156	kcal/°C

13.2. Storage Tank Heat Exchange Energy Losses (Xst)

Only heat conduction is considered in this work.

Heat exchange is by the following parts of the storage tank:

- Cylinder side (Qsts)
- Top (Qstt)
- Bottom without sleeve (Qstb)
- Sleeve flange (Qstfl)

Table 11 - Input data for storage tank heat exchange calculations

Parameter	ID	Value	Unit
conductivity of inside laminar layer – water	α_{in}	1,000	kcal/m ² °C,hr
thickness of the inner pressure tank		3	mm
thickness of the inner pressure tank	th1	0.003	m
pressure tank inside diameter		479	mm
pressure tank inside diameter	din1	0.479	m
pressure tank outside diameter		485	mm
pressure tank outside diameter	dout1	0.485	m
specific thermal conductivity of steel	λ_1	46	kcal/m°C,hr
insulation thickness		40	mm
insulation thickness	th2	0.040	m
insulation inside diameter		485	mm
insulation inside diameter	din2	0.485	m
storage tank outside diameter		565	mm
storage tank outside diameter	dout2	0.565	m
specific thermal conductivity of PU foam	λ_2	0.026	kcal/m°C,hr
conductivity of outside laminar layer - air	α_{out}	6.61	kcal/m ² °C,hr
storage tank height		1,021	mm
storage tank height for calculations		981	mm
storage tank height for calculations	H	0.981	m
top diameter		565	mm
top diameter for calculations		525	mm
top diameter for calculations	dtop	0.525	m
area of top for calculations	Atop	0.216	m ²
sleeve diameter		100	mm
sleeve diameter		0.100	m
area of sleeve cross-section	Asl	0.008	m ²
area of bottom without sleeve	Abot	0.209	m ²
sleeve flange diameter		150	mm
sleeve flange diameter	dfl	0.150	m
area of sleeve flange	Afl	0.018	m ²

Index 1 is related to inner pressure vessel made of steel 3 mm thick.

Index 2 is related to thermal insulation, 40 mm thick PU foam.

13.3. Cylinder side (Qsts)

The calculations are according to Formula 3:

$$Q = (\pi * L * \Delta t) / \{ [1 / (\alpha_{in} * d_{in1})] + [LN(d_{out1}/d_{in1}) / (2 * \lambda_1)] + [LN(d_{out2}/d_{in2}) / (2 * \lambda_2)] + [1 / (\alpha_{out} * d_{out2})] \}$$

$$L = H$$

$$Q = \pi * H * \Delta t / \Sigma r$$

$$UA = \pi * H / \Sigma r$$

$$Q = \Delta t * UA$$

Table 12 - UA heat transfer of storage tank cylinder side

Inside laminar layer thermal resistance	$1 / (\alpha_{in} * d_{in1})$	0.0021	m°C,hr/kcal
Steel pressure tank thermal resistance	$LN(d_{out1}/d_{in1}) / (2 * \lambda_1)$	0.0001	m°C,hr/kcal
Insulation thermal resistance	$LN(d_{out2}/d_{in2}) / (2 * \lambda_2)$	2.9361	m°C,hr/kcal
Outside laminar layer thermal resistance	$1 / (\alpha_{out} * d_{out2})$	0.2676	m°C,hr/kcal
Total resistance	Σr	3.2059	m°C,hr/kcal
Storage tank height for calculations	H	0.9810	m
UA heat transfer of storage tank cylinder side	$UA = \pi * H / \Sigma r$	0.9613	kcal/hr°C

$$\mathbf{Qsts = \Delta t * 0.9613 \text{ kcal/hr}^\circ\text{C}}$$

13.4. Top and Bottom (Qstt, Qstb)

The top and the bottom of the storage tank are flat from the outside. However, the inside pressure tank has spherical caps, which increase the heat transfer area. On the other hand, the thermal insulation of the top and the bottom is 40 mm thick in the center point of the sphere and much thicker on its circumference. Considering both issues, the top and bottom diameters used for calculations were reduced by

40 mm, and the height of the top and the bottom to 40 mm uniform thermal insulation.

Formula 4 - Heat transfer in flat surface

$$Q = U * A * \Delta t$$

$$UA = U * A$$

$$U = 1 / \Sigma r$$

$$UA = A / \Sigma r$$

$$Q = \Delta t * UA$$

Table 13 - UA heat transfer of storage tank top (Qstt)

Inside laminar layer thermal resistance	[$1 / \alpha_{in}$]	0.0010	m ² ,°C,hr/kcal
Steel pressure tank thermal resistance	[$th1 / \lambda 1$]	0.0001	m ² ,°C,hr/kcal
Insulation thermal resistance	[$th2 / \lambda 2$]	1.5385	m ² ,°C,hr/kcal
Outside laminar layer thermal resistance	[$1 / \alpha_{out}$]	0.1512	m ² ,°C,hr/kcal
Total resistance	Σr	1.6907	m ² ,°C,hr/kcal
Area of top for calculations	A _{top}	0.2165	m ²
UA heat transfer of storage tank top	UA = A / Σr	0.1280	kcal/hr°C

$$Q_{stt} = \Delta t * 0.128 \text{ kcal/hr}^\circ\text{C}$$

Table 14 - UA heat transfer of storage tank bottom (Qstb)

Inside laminar layer thermal resistance	[$1 / \alpha_{in}$]	0.0010	m ² ,°C,hr/kcal
Steel pressure tank thermal resistance	[$th1 / \lambda 1$]	0.0001	m ² ,°C,hr/kcal
Insulation thermal resistance	[$th2 / \lambda 2$]	1.5385	m ² ,°C,hr/kcal
Outside laminar layer thermal resistance	[$1 / \alpha_{out}$]	0.1512	m ² ,°C,hr/kcal
Total resistance	Σr	1.6907	m ² ,°C,hr/kcal
Area of bottom for calculations	A _{bot}	0.2086	m ²
UA heat transfer of storage tank bottom	UA = A / Σr	0.1234	kcal/hr°C

$$Q_{stb} = \Delta t * 0.1234 \text{ kcal/hr}^\circ\text{C}$$

Table 15 - UA heat transfer of storage tank flange (Qstfl)

Steel flange thermal resistance	$[t_{h1} / \lambda_1]$	0.0001	m ² ,°C,hr/kcal
Outside laminar layer thermal resistance	$[1 / \alpha_{out}]$	0.1512	m ² ,°C,hr/kcal
Total resistance	Σr	0.1513	m ² ,°C,hr/kcal
Area of flange	A _{fl}	0.0177	m ²
UA heat transfer of flange	UA = A / Σr	0.1168	kcal/hr°C

Sleeve's flange is not insulated.

$$Q_{stfl} = \Delta t * 0.1168 \text{ kcal/hr}^\circ\text{C}$$

13.5. Storage Tank Total UA

Table 16 - Storage tank total UA, kcal/hr°C

storage tank cylinder side, Q _{sts}	0.9613	72%
storage tank top, Q _{stt}	0.1280	10%
storage tank bottom, Q _{stb}	0.1234	9%
storage tank sleeve, Q _{stsl}	0.1168	9%
Σ UA	1.3296	100%

$$X_{st} = \Delta t * 1.3296 \text{ kcal/hr}^\circ\text{C}$$

14. Heat Exchange in Circulation Pipes

14.1. Heat Exchange

The calculations are according to Formula 3:

$$Q = (\pi * L * \Delta t) / \{ [1 / (\alpha_{in} * d_{in1})] + [LN(d_{out1}/d_{in1}) / (2 * \lambda_1)] + [LN(d_{out2}/d_{in2}) / (2 * \lambda_2)] + [1 / (\alpha_{out} * d_{out2})] \}$$

$$UA = \pi * L / \Sigma r$$

$$Q = \Delta t * UA$$

Circulation pipes are between the solar collectors array on the roof and the individual storage tanks located on each floor near the apartments.

The SWH system serves 9 upper floors of the building. The main circulation pipe serves 2 apartments on each floor, total 18 apartments.

Heat exchange calculations involve the following sections of the circulation pipes:

- Circulation pipes on the roof outside the building (XcR)
- Vertical main circulation pipes between the floors inside the building (XcB)
- Connecting pipes between the main circulation pipe to each storage tank (XcSt)

14.2. Input Data for Circulation Pipes Heat Exchange Calculations

According to the national standards pipe insulation thickness located outside should be at least 19 mm, and 13 mm inside the building.

Israeli manufacturer of thermal insulation for hot water pipes supplies EPDM foam 20 mm thick. EPDM is the perfect material for external use exposed to solar radiation.

As estimated in the section "Circulation Pipes Diameter" the main steel pipe diameter is 60.3 mm outside, 52.5 mm inside.

The plastic pipes connecting the main steel pipes to the storage tanks are 16 mm OD and 12 mm inside.

As estimated in the section "Circulation Pipes Length" the length of the main steel pipes is 100 m on the roof and 54 m inside the building per 18 apartments. The length of 16 mm OD plastic pipes is 6 m per apartment.

14.3. Circulation Pipes on Roof (XcR)Table 17 - Input data for circulation pipes on the roof (XcR)

Parameter	ID	Value	Unit
conductivity of inside laminar layer - water	α_{in}	5,000	kcal/m ² °C,hr
thickness of the steel pipe		3.9	mm
thickness of the steel pipe	th1	0.0039	m
steel pipe inside diameter		52.5	mm
steel pipe inside diameter	din1	0.0525	m
steel pipe outside diameter		60.3	mm
steel pipe outside diameter	dout1	0.0603	m
specific thermal conductivity of steel	λ_1	46	kcal/m°°C,hr
insulation thickness		20	mm
insulation thickness	th2	0.020	m
insulation inside diameter		60.3	mm
insulation inside diameter	din2	0.0603	m
insulation outside diameter		100.3	mm
insulation outside diameter	dout2	0.1003	m
specific thermal conductivity of insulation	λ_2	0.0334	kcal/m°°C,hr
conductivity of outside laminar layer - air	α_{out}	21.50	kcal/m ² °C,hr
pipes total length	L	100	m

Table 18 - UA heat transfer losses in steel circulation pipes on the roof (XcR)

Inside laminar layer thermal resistance	$1 / (\alpha_{in} * din1)$	0.0038	M°°C,hr/kcal
Steel pipe thermal resistance	$LN(dout1/din1) / (2 * \lambda_1)$	0.0015	M°°C,hr/kcal
Insulation thermal resistance	$LN(dout2/din2) / (2 * \lambda_2)$	7.6259	M°°C,hr/kcal
Outside laminar layer thermal resistance	$1 / (\alpha_{out} * dout2)$	0.4638	M°°C,hr/kcal
Total resistance	Σr	8.0951	M°°C,hr/kcal
Pipes length	L	100	m
UA heat transfer per 18 apartments	$UA_{18} = \pi * L / \Sigma r$	38.8087	kcal/hr°°C
UA heat transfer per apartment	$UA = UA_{18} / 18$	2.1560	kcal/hr°°C

$$\mathbf{XcR = \Delta t * 2.156 \text{ kcal/hr}^\circ\text{C}}$$

14.4. Main Circulation Pipes Between Floors Inside the Building (XcB)Table 19 - Input data for main circulation pipes inside the building (XcB)

Parameter	ID	Value	Unit
conductivity of inside laminar layer – water	α_{in}	5,000	kcal/m ² °C,hr
thickness of the steel pipe		3.9	Mm
thickness of the steel pipe	th1	0.0039	M
steel pipe inside diameter		52.5	Mm
steel pipe inside diameter	din1	0.0525	M
steel pipe outside diameter		60.3	Mm
steel pipe outside diameter	dout1	0.0603	M
specific thermal conductivity of steel	λ_1	46	kcal/m°°C,hr
insulation thickness		13	Mm
insulation thickness	th2	0.013	M
insulation inside diameter		60.3	Mm
insulation inside diameter	din2	0.0603	M
insulation outside diameter		86.3	Mm
insulation outside diameter	dout2	0.0863	M
insulation specific thermal conductivity	λ_2	0.0334	kcal/m°°C,hr
conductivity of outside laminar layer – air	α_{out}	6.61	kcal/m ² °C,hr
pipes length per 18 apartments	L	54	M

Table 20 - UA heat transfer losses in steel circulation pipes inside the building (XcB)

Inside laminar layer thermal resistance	$1 / (\alpha_{in} * din1)$	0.0038	m°°C,hr/kcal
Steel pipe thermal resistance	$LN(dout1/din1) / (2 * \lambda_1)$	0.0015	m°°C,hr/kcal
Insulation thermal resistance	$LN(dout2/din2) / (2 * \lambda_2)$	5.3728	m°°C,hr/kcal
Outside laminar layer thermal resistance	$1 / (\alpha_{out} * dout2)$	1.7519	m°°C,hr/kcal
Total resistance	Σr	7.1301	m°°C,hr/kcal
Pipes length	L	54	M
UA heat transfer per 18 apartments	$UA_{18} = \pi * L / \Sigma r$	23.7930	kcal/hr°°C
UA heat transfer per apartment	$UA = UA_{18} / 18$	1.3218	kcal/hr°°C

$$\mathbf{XcB = \Delta t * 1.3218 \text{ kcal/hr}^\circ\text{C}}$$

14.5. Plastic Circulation Pipes in Building to Each Storage Tank (XcSt)Table 21 - Input data for plastic circulation pipes to each storage tank (XcSt)

Parameter	ID	Value	Unit
conductivity of inside laminar layer - water	α_{in}	5,000	kcal/m ² °C,hr
thickness of pipe		2	Mm
thickness of pipe	th1	0.002	M
plastic pipe inside diameter		12	Mm
plastic pipe inside diameter	din1	0.012	M
plastic pipe outside diameter		16	Mm
plastic pipe outside diameter	dout1	0.016	M
specific thermal conductivity of plastic	λ_1	0.301	kcal/m°°C,hr
insulation thickness		13	Mm
insulation thickness	th2	0.013	M
insulation inside diameter		16	Mm
insulation inside diameter	din2	0.016	M
insulation outside diameter		42	Mm
insulation outside diameter	dout2	0.042	M
insulation specific thermal conductivity	λ_2	0.0334	kcal/m°°C,hr
conductivity of outside laminar layer - air	α_{out}	6.61	kcal/m ² °C,hr
pipes length per apartment	L	6	M

Table 22 - UA heat transfer losses in plastic circulation pipes to each storage tank (XcSt)

Inside laminar layer thermal resistance	$1 / (\alpha_{in} * din1)$	0.0167	m°°C,hr/kcal
Plastic pipe thermal resistance	$LN(dout1/din1) / (2 * \lambda_1)$	0.4780	m°°C,hr/kcal
Insulation thermal resistance	$LN(dout2/din2) / (2 * \lambda_2)$	14.4638	m°°C,hr/kcal
Outside laminar layer thermal resistance	$1 / (\alpha_{out} * dout2)$	3.5998	m°°C,hr/kcal
Total resistance	Σr	18.5582	m°°C,hr/kcal
Pipes length	L	6	M
UA heat transfer per apartment	$UA = \pi * L / \Sigma r$	1.0157	kcal/hr°°C

$$XcSt = \Delta t * 1.0157 \text{ kcal/hr}^\circ\text{C}$$

14.6. Circulation Pipes Total UA per ApartmentTable 23 - Circulation pipes total UA per apartment, kcal/hr°°C

steel circulation pipes on the roof (QcircR)	2.1560	48%
steel circulation pipes inside the building (QcircB)	1.3218	29%
plastic circulation pipes to each storage tank (QcircSt)	1.0157	23%
Σ UA	4.4936	100%

Circulation pipes total heat transfer losses X_c , kcal/hr:

$$X_c = \Delta t * 4.4936 \text{ kcal/hr}^\circ\text{C}$$

15. Simulation of Storage Tank Hourly Temperature

Determination of heat exchange energy losses requires storage tank temperature. However, the storage tank temperature depends on the circulation pipes' heat exchange energy losses. This results in circular calculations and may be solved by simulation.

The simulation time step (integration period) is 1 hour.

Solar energy from the collectors array, SE , is transferred by the circulation pipes to the storage tank. Part of this energy will be lost in the circulation pipes and storage tank envelop, and all the rest will heat the water in the storage tank.

The simulation includes heat exchange energy losses and does not include thermal mass energy losses.

The useful energy in the storage tank is SE_{est} .

$$SE_{est} = SE - Loss$$

The SE_{est} energy will heat the storage tank water according to Formula 1.

$$SE_{est} = m * c * (t - t_0)$$

$$MC = m * c$$

$$t = t_0 + SE_{est} / MC$$

MC is the thermal mass of the storage tank including water, determined in the section "*Storage Tank Heat Transfer*".

$$MC = 156 \text{ kcal}/^\circ\text{C}$$

Formula 5 - Storage tank temperature

$$t = t_0 + (SE - \text{Loss}) / MC$$

$$\text{Loss} = (t_0 - T_a) * 5.8232 \text{ kcal/hr}^\circ\text{C}$$

$$t = t_0 + (SE - (t_0 - T_a) * 5.8232 \text{ kcal/hr}^\circ\text{C}) / MC$$

t storage tank current temperature, °C

t₀ storage tank temperature before one hour, °C

MC thermal mass of the storage tank including water, kcal/°C

SE solar energy supplied by the solar collectors for one apartment, kcal/hr

Loss energy loss in circulation pipes and storage tank envelop, kcal/hr

T_a ambient temperature, °C

The storage tank temperature calculations are for one apartment.

Table 24 - Storage tank water temperature, °C

	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19
January			7.7	7.9	9.1	11.8	15.5	20.1	25.0	29.7	33.4	35.5	36.4	35.9	35.2	34.4
February			8.7	8.9	10.3	13.9	17.7	22.0	26.3	30.8	35.1	37.3	39.4	39.9	39.1	38.1
March		9.2	9.3	9.8	11.5	14.8	19.2	24.4	30.1	35.7	40.5	44.0	45.9	46.3	45.5	44.4
April		13.3	13.7	14.8	17.3	21.1	26.0	31.6	37.2	42.7	46.5	49.2	50.7	50.8	50.1	49.0
May	15.1	15.3	16.2	18.0	21.0	25.3	30.5	36.0	41.5	46.5	50.6	53.3	54.6	54.7	54.1	52.9
June	18.4	18.7	19.4	21.1	23.9	27.9	33.0	38.6	44.4	49.8	54.3	57.6	59.6	60.1	59.7	58.6
July	19.9	20.0	20.7	22.0	24.3	27.6	32.4	37.9	43.6	49.1	53.8	57.4	59.6	60.3	59.9	58.8
August		20.1	20.6	21.7	24.0	27.9	33.0	38.8	45.0	50.5	55.5	59.2	61.3	61.7	61.1	59.9
September		18.8	19.3	20.7	23.8	28.3	32.9	38.1	44.6	49.6	54.6	57.3	58.3	58.4	57.5	56.4
October		16.3	16.6	18.0	20.6	25.9	31.3	36.1	40.5	45.4	48.7	50.4	51.2	50.9	49.9	48.9
November			11.2	12.5	15.5	19.8	24.8	30.3	35.5	40.0	43.3	45.0	45.0	44.2	43.3	42.4
December			8.1	8.4	9.4	12.4	16.7	21.6	26.1	30.3	32.7	36.4	37.0	36.4	35.6	34.8

Table 25 - Storage tank maximum water temperature without backup, TstMax, °C

hr -->	8:00	12:00	16:00	19:00	TstMax
January	9.1	33.4	36.4	34.4	36.4
February	10.3	35.1	39.4	38.1	39.9
March	11.5	40.5	45.9	44.4	46.3
April	17.3	46.5	50.7	49.0	50.8
May	21.0	50.6	54.6	52.9	54.7
June	23.9	54.3	59.6	58.6	60.1
July	24.3	53.8	59.6	58.8	60.3
August	24.0	55.5	61.3	59.9	61.7
September	23.8	54.6	58.3	56.4	58.4
October	20.6	48.7	51.2	48.9	51.2
November	15.5	43.3	45.0	42.4	45.0
December	9.4	32.7	37.0	34.8	37.0
Ave	17.6	45.7	49.9	48.2	50.2

16. Circulation Pipes Heat Transfer Energy Losses

It is assumed in this work that the circulation pump control allows efficient utilization of solar radiation, starting circulation when the water in the solar collector is slightly warmer than in the storage tanks and ending circulation in the last solar hour of the day.

16.1. Energy Losses in Main Circulation Pipes on Roof (XcR)

$$\mathbf{XcR = \Delta t * 2.156 \text{ kcal/hr}^\circ\text{C}}$$

$$\mathbf{\Delta t = T_{st} - T_a}$$

Table 26 - Energy losses in main circulation pipes on roof, XcR, kcal/hr

hr -->	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	kcal/d
January	0.0	0.3	0.2	-0.5	1.2	7.9	16.4	25.8	33.5	39.3	42.7	0.0	0.0	0.0	166.9
February	0.0	0.0	-3.0	-0.1	4.3	11.5	18.6	28.2	37.5	43.1	49.3	0.0	0.0	0.0	189.4
March	0.2	-0.1	-3.6	-1.8	3.8	12.7	23.7	35.3	44.8	52.9	58.5	61.7	0.0	0.0	288.1
April	0.4	-1.4	-2.8	1.7	9.3	19.4	30.4	42.4	51.1	58.0	61.7	64.1	0.0	0.0	334.1
May	1.0	0.4	-1.1	5.0	13.7	24.9	36.2	47.3	56.3	63.0	66.6	68.2	0.0	0.0	381.5
June	0.6	-1.7	-1.3	3.6	12.5	23.1	35.0	47.0	57.2	64.9	70.2	72.5	0.0	0.0	383.6
July	0.3	-3.3	-4.0	-0.6	7.1	17.9	29.6	41.7	52.2	60.2	66.0	68.9	0.0	0.0	336.0
August	-0.1	-3.9	-5.6	-0.5	7.7	18.3	31.4	43.2	54.3	62.8	68.6	71.1	0.0	0.0	347.2
September	1.0	-1.8	-4.3	2.1	9.1	18.7	31.8	42.4	52.9	59.7	62.9	65.0	0.0	0.0	339.5
October	1.4	0.4	-3.3	2.7	11.8	20.3	29.3	39.4	47.0	51.4	54.4	0.0	0.0	0.0	255.0
November	0.0	2.2	1.2	4.1	10.9	18.6	28.8	38.2	45.6	49.7	51.4	0.0	0.0	0.0	250.7
December	0.0	0.4	-3.1	-4.1	0.3	6.6	15.1	24.2	29.7	38.1	41.3	0.0	0.0	0.0	148.5

Table 27 - Energy losses in main circulation pipes on roof, XcR, kWh per month, per apartment

	kcal/d	kWh/d	kWh/month
January	166.9	0.19	6.0
February	189.4	0.22	6.2
March	288.1	0.34	10.4
April	334.1	0.39	11.7
May	381.5	0.44	13.8
June	383.6	0.45	13.4
July	336.0	0.39	12.1
August	347.2	0.40	12.5
September	339.5	0.39	11.8
October	255.0	0.30	9.2
November	250.7	0.29	8.7
December	148.5	0.17	5.4
Σ			121.1
to SE			4.5%

16.2. Energy Losses in Main Circulation Pipes Between Floors inside the Building
(XcB)

$$\mathbf{XcB = \Delta t * 1.3218 \text{ kcal/hr}^\circ\text{C}}$$

$$\mathbf{\Delta t = Tst - Tb}$$

Table 28 - Energy losses in main circulation pipes inside the building, XcB, kcal/hr

hr -->	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	kcal/d
January	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	5.3	11.7	18.1	22.9	25.6	26.8	0.0	0.0	0.0	110.4
February	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	1.4	7.0	12.7	18.6	24.4	27.2	30.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	121.2
March	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	1.3	8.2	15.8	23.2	29.6	34.2	36.7	37.2	0.0	0.0	186.2
April	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	5.3	12.7	20.0	27.3	32.3	36.0	37.9	38.1	0.0	0.0	209.4
May	0.0	0.0	0.0	1.7	8.5	15.8	23.1	29.7	35.1	38.7	40.5	40.5	0.0	0.0	233.6
June	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.7	7.4	14.9	22.5	29.6	35.6	40.0	42.6	43.3	0.0	0.0	236.7
July	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	4.3	11.6	19.1	26.3	32.6	37.3	40.2	41.2	0.0	0.0	212.7
August	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	4.6	12.2	20.5	27.7	34.3	39.2	42.0	42.6	0.0	0.0	223.1
September	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	5.7	12.5	21.1	27.7	34.3	37.9	39.2	39.4	0.0	0.0	217.7
October	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.1	7.3	13.5	19.4	25.9	30.3	32.4	33.5	0.0	0.0	0.0	162.4
November	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	5.7	12.8	19.7	25.8	30.1	32.4	32.4	0.0	0.0	0.0	158.9
December	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	5.9	11.9	17.5	20.6	25.5	26.3	0.0	0.0	0.0	107.6

Table 29 - Energy losses in main circulation pipes inside the building, XcB, kWh per month, per apartment

	kcal/d	kWh/d	kWh/month
January	110.4	0.13	4.0
February	121.2	0.14	3.9
March	186.2	0.22	6.7
April	209.4	0.24	7.3
May	233.6	0.27	8.4
June	236.7	0.28	8.3
July	212.7	0.25	7.7
August	223.1	0.26	8.0
September	217.7	0.25	7.6
October	162.4	0.19	5.9
November	158.9	0.18	5.5
December	107.6	0.13	3.9
Σ			77.2
to SE			2.9%

16.3. Energy Losses in Circulation Pipes to Each Storage Tank (XcSt)

$$XcSt = \Delta t * 1.0157 \text{ kcal/hr}^\circ\text{C}$$

$$\Delta t = Tst - Tb$$

Table 30 - Energy losses in circulation pipes to each storage tank, XcSt, kcal/hr

hr -->	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	kcal/d
January	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	4.1	9.0	13.9	17.6	19.7	20.6	0.0	0.0	0.0	84.9
February	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	1.0	5.4	9.8	14.3	18.7	20.9	23.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	93.1
March	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	1.0	6.3	12.2	17.9	22.7	26.3	28.2	28.5	0.0	0.0	143.1
April	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	4.0	9.7	15.4	21.0	24.8	27.6	29.1	29.2	0.0	0.0	160.9
May	0.0	0.0	0.0	1.3	6.5	12.1	17.7	22.9	27.0	29.8	31.1	31.1	0.0	0.0	179.5
June	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.6	5.7	11.4	17.3	22.8	27.4	30.7	32.7	33.3	0.0	0.0	181.9
July	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	3.3	8.9	14.7	20.2	25.0	28.7	30.9	31.7	0.0	0.0	163.4
August	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	3.5	9.4	15.7	21.3	26.4	30.1	32.2	32.7	0.0	0.0	171.4
September	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	4.4	9.6	16.2	21.3	26.3	29.1	30.1	30.3	0.0	0.0	167.3
October	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.1	5.6	10.4	14.9	19.9	23.3	24.9	25.7	0.0	0.0	0.0	124.8
November	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	4.4	9.9	15.2	19.8	23.1	24.9	24.9	0.0	0.0	0.0	122.1
December	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	4.5	9.1	13.4	15.8	19.6	20.2	0.0	0.0	0.0	82.7

Table 31 - Energy losses in circulation pipes to each storage tank, XcSt, kWh per month, per apartment

	kcal/d	kWh/d	kWh/month
January	84.9	0.10	3.1
February	93.1	0.11	3.0
March	143.1	0.17	5.2
April	160.9	0.19	5.6
May	179.5	0.21	6.5
June	181.9	0.21	6.3
July	163.4	0.19	5.9
August	171.4	0.20	6.2
September	167.3	0.19	5.8
October	124.8	0.15	4.5
November	122.1	0.14	4.3
December	82.7	0.10	3.0
Σ			59.3
to SE			2.2%

16.4. Heat Transfer Energy Losses in Circulation Pipes (Xc)

$$\mathbf{Xc = XcR + XcB + XcSt}$$

Table 32 - Heat transfer energy losses in circulation pipes, Xc, kWh per month, per apartment

	XcR	XcB	XcSt	Xc	XcR	XcB	XcSt	Xc
	kcal/d	kcal/d	kcal/d	kcal/d	kWh/m	kWh/m	kWh/m	kWh/m
January	166.9	110.4	84.9	362.2	6.0	4.0	3.1	13.1
February	189.4	121.2	93.1	403.7	6.2	3.9	3.0	13.1
March	288.1	186.2	143.1	617.4	10.4	6.7	5.2	22.3
April	334.1	209.4	160.9	704.5	11.7	7.3	5.6	24.6
May	381.5	233.6	179.5	794.6	13.8	8.4	6.5	28.6
June	383.6	236.7	181.9	802.2	13.4	8.3	6.3	28.0
July	336.0	212.7	163.4	712.1	12.1	7.7	5.9	25.7
August	347.2	223.1	171.4	741.7	12.5	8.0	6.2	26.7
September	339.5	217.7	167.3	724.6	11.8	7.6	5.8	25.3
October	255.0	162.4	124.8	542.1	9.2	5.9	4.5	19.5
November	250.7	158.9	122.1	531.6	8.7	5.5	4.3	18.5
December	148.5	107.6	82.7	338.9	5.4	3.9	3.0	12.2
Σ					121.1	77.2	59.3	257.7
to SE					4.5%	2.9%	2.2%	9.5%

Energy losses in the circulation pipes are 256 kWh per year, 9.5% of the energy supplied by the solar collectors.

17. Storage Tank Heat Exchange Energy Losses

Storage tank heat exchange energy losses (Xst):

$$\mathbf{Xst = \Delta t * 1.3296 \text{ kcal/hr}^\circ\text{C}}$$

$$\mathbf{\Delta t = Tst - Tb}$$

Table 33 - Storage tank heat exchange losses, Xst, kcal/hr

hr -->	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	kcal/d
January	0	0	0	0	0	5	12	18	23	26	27	26	27	45	210
February	0	0	0	0	1	7	13	19	24	27	30	31	30	45	227
March	0	0	0	0	1	8	16	23	30	34	37	37	36	43	266
April	0	0	0	0	5	13	20	27	33	36	38	38	37	37	285
May	0	0	0	2	9	16	23	30	35	39	41	41	40	38	313
June	0	0	0	1	7	15	23	30	36	40	43	44	43	42	323
July	0	0	0	0	4	12	19	26	33	38	40	41	41	39	294
August	0	0	0	0	5	12	21	28	35	39	42	43	42	40	307
September	0	0	0	0	6	13	21	28	34	38	39	40	38	37	294
October	0	0	0	0	7	14	20	26	30	33	34	33	32	32	261
November	0	0	0	0	6	13	20	26	30	33	33	31	30	39	261
December	0	0	0	0	0	6	12	18	21	26	26	26	26	44	204

Table 34 - Storage tank heat exchange losses, Xst

	kcal/d	kWh/d	kWh/month
January	210.3	0.24	7.6
February	227.0	0.26	7.4
March	266.2	0.31	9.6
April	285.3	0.33	10.0
May	313.3	0.36	11.3
June	322.7	0.38	11.3
July	294.2	0.34	10.6
August	306.8	0.36	11.1
September	294.3	0.34	10.3
October	261.0	0.30	9.4
November	261.0	0.30	9.1
December	204.0	0.24	7.4
Σ			114.9
to SE			4.3%

18. Energy Loss in Thermal Mass of Circulation Pipes

Water circulation is stopped at the highest daily water temperature. After the circulation pump stops, the hot water in the pipe cannot be used and is wasted.

18.1. Thermal Mass of Circulation Pipes on Roof

Table 35 - Thermal mass of circulation pipes on roof for 18 apartments (MCcircR)

steel pipe inside diameter		52.5	mm
steel pipe inside diameter	din1	0.0525	m
cross-section area	Ain1	0.0022	m ²
steel pipe outside diameter		60.3	mm
steel pipe outside diameter	Dout1	0.0603	m
cross-section area	Aout1	0.0029	m ²
cross-section area	A1	0.0007	m ²
pipe length	L	100	m
steel pipe volume	V1	0.07	m ³
steel density	ρ_1	7,800	Kg/m ³
steel pipe mass	m1	539	kg
steel specific heat	c1	0.12	kcal/kg°C
thermal mass steel pipe	MC1	64.68	kcal/°C
insulation inside diameter		60.3	mm
insulation inside diameter	din2	0.0603	m
cross-section area	Ain2	0.0029	m ²
insulation outside diameter		100.3	mm
insulation outside diameter	Dout2	0.1003	m
cross-section area	Aout2	0.0079	m ²
cross-section area	A2	0.0050	m ²
insulation volume	V2	0.50	m ³
insulation density	ρ_2	85	Kg/m ³
insulation mass	m2	43	kg
insulation specific heat	c2	0.48	kcal/kg°C
insulation thermal mass	MC2	20.49	kcal/°C
water in pipe volume	Ain1*L	0.22	m ³
water density	ρ_w	1,000	Kg/m ³
water in pipe mass	Mw	216	kg
water specific heat	Cw	1.00	kcal/kg°C
water in pipe thermal mass	MCw	216	kcal/°C
total thermal mass 18 apartments		302	kcal/°C
thermal mass per apartment	MCcircR	16.76	kcal/°C

Table 36 - Energy loss in thermal mass of main circulation pipes on roof, McR, kWh per month per apartment

	Tc °C	TstMax °C	McR kcal/d	McR kWh/month
January	15.1	36.4	357	12.9
February	15.7	39.9	406	13.2
March	17.2	46.3	488	17.6
April	20.0	50.8	517	18.0
May	20.0	54.7	580	20.9
June	23.4	60.1	617	21.5
July	25.1	60.3	590	21.3
August	25.5	61.7	607	21.9
September	24.6	58.4	567	19.8
October	21.8	51.2	492	17.7
November	19.5	45.0	427	14.9
December	16.1	37.0	350	12.6
Σ				212.3
to SE				7.9%

18.2. Thermal Mass of Main Circulation Pipes Between Floors Inside the BuildingTable 37 - Thermal mass of main circulation pipes between floors inside the building for 18 apartments (MCcircB)

steel pipe inside diameter		52.5	mm
steel pipe inside diameter	din1	0.0525	m
cross-section area	Ain1	0.0022	m ²
steel pipe outside diameter		60.3	mm
steel pipe outside diameter	Dout1	0.0603	m
cross-section area	Aout1	0.0029	m ²
cross-section area	A1	0.0007	m ²
pipe length	L	54	m
steel pipe volume	V1	0.04	m ³
steel density	ρ1	7,800	kg/m ³
steel pipe mass	m1	291	kg
steel specific heat	c1	0.12	kcal/kg°C
thermal mass steel pipe	MC1	34.93	kcal/°C
insulation inside diameter		60.3	mm
insulation inside diameter	din2	0.0603	m
cross-section area	Ain2	0.0029	m ²
insulation outside diameter		86.3	mm
insulation outside diameter	Dout2	0.0863	m
cross-section area	Aout2	0.0058	m ²
cross-section area	A2	0.0030	m ²
insulation volume	V2	0.16	m ³
insulation density	ρ2	85	kg/m ³
insulation mass	m2	14	kg
insulation specific heat	c2	0.48	kcal/kg°C
insulation thermal mass	MC2	6.56	kcal/°C
water in pipe volume	Ain1*L	0.12	m ³
water density	ρw	1,000	kg/m ³
water in pipe mass	Mw	117	kg
water specific heat	Cw	1.00	kcal/kg°C
water in pipe thermal mass	MCw	117	kcal/°C
total thermal mass 18 apartments		158	kcal/°C
thermal mass per apartment	MCcircB	8.80	kcal/°C

Table 38 - Energy loss in thermal mass of main circulation pipes in building, McB, kWh per month per apartment

	Tb °C	TstMax °C	McB kcal/d	McB kWh/month
January	16.1	36.4	178	6.4
February	16.7	39.9	204	7.4
March	18.2	46.3	247	8.9
April	22.0	50.8	253	9.1
May	24.0	54.7	270	9.7
June	27.4	60.1	289	10.4
July	29.1	60.3	274	9.9
August	29.5	61.7	283	10.2
September	28.6	58.4	262	9.5
October	25.8	51.2	223	8.0
November	20.5	45.0	216	7.8
December	17.1	37.0	175	6.3
Σ				103.7
to SE				3.8%

18.3. Thermal Mass of Circulation Pipes to Storage TankTable 39 - Thermal mass of circulation pipes to storage tank (MCcircSt)

plastic pipe inside diameter		12	mm
plastic pipe inside diameter	din1	0.012	m
cross-section area	Ain1	0.0001	m ²
plastic pipe outside diameter		16	mm
plastic pipe outside diameter	dout1	0.016	m
cross-section area	Aout1	0.0002	m ²
cross-section area	A1	0.0001	m ²
pipe length	L	6	m
pipe volume	V1	0.001	m ³
plastic density	ρ1	938	kg/m ³
pipe mass	m1	0.5	kg
plastic specific heat	c1	0.55	kcal/kg°C
thermal mass pipe	MC1	0.27	kcal/°C
insulation inside diameter		16	mm
insulation inside diameter	din2	0.016	m
cross-section area	Ain2	0.0002	m ²
insulation outside diameter		42	mm
insulation outside diameter	dout2	0.042	m
cross-section area	Aout2	0.0014	m ²
cross-section area	A2	0.0012	m ²
insulation volume	V2	0.01	m ³
insulation density	ρ2	85	kg/m ³
insulation mass	m2	0.6	kg
insulation specific heat	c2	0.48	kcal/kg°C
insulation thermal mass	MC2	0.29	kcal/°C
water in pipe volume	Ain1*L	0.001	m ³
water density	ρw	1,000	kg/m ³
water in pipe mass	mw	0.7	kg
water specific heat	cw	1.00	kcal/kg°C
water in pipe thermal mass	MCw	0.7	kcal/°C
thermal mass per apartment	MCcircSt	1.2	kcal/°C

Table 40 - Energy loss in thermal mass of circulation pipes to storage tank, McSt, kWh per month per apartment

	Tb °C	TstMax °C	McSt kcal/d	McSt kWh/month
January	16.1	36.4	25	0.9
February	16.7	39.9	29	1.0
March	18.2	46.3	35	1.3
April	22.0	50.8	36	1.3
May	24.0	54.7	38	1.4
June	27.4	60.1	41	1.5
July	29.1	60.3	39	1.4
August	29.5	61.7	40	1.4
September	28.6	58.4	37	1.3
October	25.8	51.2	31	1.1
November	20.5	45.0	30	1.1
December	17.1	37.0	25	0.9
Σ				14.6
to SE				0.5%

18.4. Energy Loss in Thermal Mass of Circulation Pipes

$$\mathbf{Mc = McR + McB + McSt}$$

- Mc energy losses in thermal mass of circulation pipes after the end of circulation, kcal/day
- McB energy losses in thermal mass of circulation pipes between floors, after the end of circulation, kcal/day
- McR energy losses in thermal mass of circulation pipes on the roof, after the end of circulation, kcal/day
- McSt energy losses in thermal mass of circulation pipes from main pipes between the floors to the storage tank, after the end of circulation, kcal/day

Table 41 - Total energy losses in thermal mass of circulation pipes, Mc, kWh per month per apartment

	McR kcal/d	McB kcal/d	McSt kcal/d	Mc kcal/d	McR kWh/m	McB kWh/m	McSt kWh/m	Mc kWh/m
January	357	178	25	560	12.9	6.4	0.9	20.2
February	406	204	29	639	13.2	6.7	0.9	20.8
March	488	247	35	770	17.6	8.9	1.3	27.8
April	517	253	36	806	18.0	8.8	1.2	28.1
May	580	270	38	888	20.9	9.7	1.4	32.0
June	617	289	41	946	21.5	10.1	1.4	33.0
July	590	274	39	903	21.3	9.9	1.4	32.5
August	607	283	40	930	21.9	10.2	1.4	33.5
September	567	262	37	866	19.8	9.2	1.3	30.2
October	492	223	31	746	17.7	8.0	1.1	26.9
November	427	216	30	673	14.9	7.5	1.1	23.5
December	350	175	25	550	12.6	6.3	0.9	19.8
Σ					212.3	101.8	14.3	328.3
to SE					7.9%	3.8%	0.5%	12.1%

The energy loss in thermal mass of the circulation pipes is 328 kWh/y, 12% of the energy supplied by the solar collectors.

19. Energy Loss in Thermal Mass of Solar Collector

$$M_{sc} = \Delta t * MC_{sc}$$

$$\Delta t = T_{stMax} - T_{aMin}$$

- M_{sc} energy loss in thermal mass of solar collector after the end of circulation, kcal/day
- MC_{sc} thermal mass of solar collector per apartment, kcal/°C
- T_{stMax} storage tank maximum temperature without backup, °C
- T_{aMin} ambient temperature at sunrise, °C

Table 42 - Thermal mass of solar collector, MC_{sc}, kcal/°C

Solar collector MC per 1 m ²		3.86	kcal/°C,m ²
Solar collector area per apartment		2.21	m ²
Thermal mass of solar collector per apartment	MC _{sc}	8.5478	kcal/°C

Table 43 - Energy loss in thermal mass of solar collector, M_{sc}, kWh per month per apartment

	T _{aMin} °C	T _{stMax} °C	M _{sc} kcal/d	M _{sc} kWh/month
January	7.8	36.4	244	8.8
February	8.9	39.9	265	8.6
March	9.2	46.3	317	11.4
April	13.5	50.8	319	11.1
May	15.0	54.7	339	12.2
June	18.1	60.1	360	12.6
July	19.8	60.3	347	12.5
August	20.7	61.7	351	12.6
September	18.8	58.4	339	11.8
October	16.0	51.2	301	10.8
November	11.5	45.0	287	10.0
December	8.2	37.0	246	8.9
Σ to SE				131.5 4.9%

20. Energy Stored in Storage Tank Considering Heat Transfer Energy Losses

Every hour the solar collectors will add energy to the storage tank reduced by the heat transfer energy losses in the circulation pipes and the storage tank.

$$\text{Est} = \text{SE} - \text{Xc} - \text{Xst}$$

Est energy stored in the storage tank
 SE solar energy leaving collectors for a single apartment
 Xc heat exchange energy losses in circulation pipes
 Xst heat exchange energy losses of storage tank

The above formula does not include thermal mass energy losses, as the hot water temperature was not calculated before the simulation of the storage tank temperature. This may result in higher storage tank temperature which shall contribute to the conservativeness of the calculations (over-estimated losses). The calculations including heat exchange and thermal mass energy losses are in the next section "Energy Stored in Storage Tank Considering Heat Transfer and Thermal Mass Energy Losses".

Table 44 - Energy added every hour to the storage tank, kcal/hr

hr -->	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	kcal/d
January	0	23	196	418	577	723	757	749	567	328	139	-66	-116	-127	4167
February	0	27	234	549	607	666	677	701	678	333	334	83	-131	-146	4610
March	14	88	271	507	686	810	906	876	748	550	301	50	-127	-170	5508
April	63	181	379	598	772	876	867	862	598	432	226	22	-120	-174	5582
May	134	281	474	674	804	861	863	790	632	430	208	2	-94	-174	5885
June	108	265	439	630	790	883	905	841	711	513	315	86	-65	-170	6251
July	108	205	356	511	753	865	892	851	740	562	346	116	-74	-160	6071
August	77	161	362	623	793	899	980	854	786	573	328	70	-95	-183	6228
September	76	215	485	713	723	811	1014	778	779	426	161	21	-148	-177	5877
October	58	208	415	826	849	743	698	763	521	255	124	-49	-149	-152	5111
November	0	203	465	670	796	847	819	711	517	265	2	-127	-142	-145	4883
December	0	50	162	465	666	768	704	666	372	573	100	-96	-116	-124	4189
Ave	53	159	353	599	735	813	840	787	637	437	215	9	-115	-158	5363
Min	0	23	162	418	577	666	677	666	372	255	2	-127	-149	-183	4167
Max	134	281	485	826	849	899	1014	876	786	573	346	116	-65	-124	6251

The negative values in the above table indicate that in these hours the losses are higher than the solar energy.

Table 45 - Energy stored in the storage tank, kcal/hr

hr -->	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19
January	0	23	219	637	1213	1936	2693	3442	4009	4338	4476	4411	4294	4167
February	0	27	261	809	1416	2082	2759	3460	4138	4471	4805	4888	4757	4610
March	14	102	372	879	1565	2375	3281	4157	4905	5454	5755	5804	5678	5508
April	63	244	623	1221	1993	2869	3736	4598	5196	5628	5853	5875	5756	5582
May	134	415	889	1563	2367	3228	4091	4881	5513	5944	6152	6154	6059	5885
June	108	373	813	1442	2232	3115	4020	4861	5572	6086	6400	6486	6421	6251
July	108	313	669	1180	1934	2799	3691	4541	5281	5844	6190	6305	6231	6071
August	77	238	600	1222	2015	2914	3894	4748	5534	6107	6436	6506	6411	6228
September	76	291	776	1488	2211	3022	4036	4814	5593	6020	6180	6202	6054	5877
October	58	266	681	1507	2356	3099	3797	4560	5081	5337	5461	5412	5263	5111
November	0	203	668	1338	2134	2981	3800	4512	5029	5294	5296	5169	5027	4883
December	0	50	212	676	1342	2110	2814	3480	3852	4425	4525	4429	4313	4189
Ave	53	212	565	1164	1898	2711	3551	4338	4975	5412	5627	5637	5522	5363
Min	0	23	212	637	1213	1936	2693	3442	3852	4338	4476	4411	4294	4167
Max	134	415	889	1563	2367	3228	4091	4881	5593	6107	6436	6506	6421	6251

Table 46 - Energy stored in the storage tank, per apartment, per month and per year

	kcal/day	kWh/day	kcal/month	kWh/month
January	4,167	4.85	129,187	150
February	4,610	5.36	129,091	150
March	5,508	6.41	170,741	199
April	5,582	6.49	167,464	195
May	5,885	6.84	182,431	212
June	6,251	7.27	187,517	218
July	6,071	7.06	188,189	219
August	6,228	7.24	193,074	225
September	5,877	6.83	176,310	205
October	5,111	5.94	158,441	184
November	4,883	5.68	146,476	170
December	4,189	4.87	129,870	151
Σ			1,958,791	2,278
to SE				84.3%

21. Energy Stored in Storage Tank Considering Heat Transfer and Thermal Mass Energy Losses

$$\text{Est} = \text{SE} - \text{Xc} - \text{Xst} - \text{Mc} - \text{Msc}$$

Est	energy stored in storage tank
SE	solar energy leaving collectors for a single apartment
Xc	heat exchange energy losses in circulation pipes
Xst	heat exchange energy losses of storage tank
Mc	energy losses in thermal mass of circulation pipes
Msc	energy losses in thermal mass of solar collectors

Table 47 - Energy stored in storage tank considering heat transfer and thermal mass energy losses

	SE	Xc	Xst	Mc	Msc	Est	Est
	kcal/d	kcal/d	kcal/d	kcal/d	kcal/d	kcal/d	kWh/m
January	4,863	362	210	560	244	3,486	126
February	5,410	404	227	639	265	3,875	126
March	6,456	617	266	770	317	4,485	162
April	6,662	704	285	806	319	4,547	159
May	7,142	795	313	888	339	4,807	173
June	7,531	802	323	946	360	5,101	178
July	7,193	712	294	903	347	4,937	178
August	7,361	742	307	930	351	5,032	181
September	6,972	725	294	866	339	4,749	166
October	6,103	542	261	746	301	4,254	153
November	5,846	532	261	673	287	4,093	143
December	4,830	339	204	550	246	3,491	126
Σ to SE							1,871 69.2%

22. Energy Demand for Hot Water

According to [1] the energy actually used to heat water in 120 liters storage tank is equivalent to 1,450 kWh/y. This is based on the Israel Electric Company surveys from years when electric water heaters had separate meters and switches to operate only in off-peak hours [2], [3].

The electricity consumption of 120 liters electric heaters was 1,200 kWh/y on the national average [1], [2], [3]. At the same time, the consumption of electricity for backup of 120 liters solar water heaters was 250 kWh/y.

The estimation of use of 1,450 kWh/y with 120 liters SWH is related to the quality of life; families having solar water heater use more hot water than families having electric water heater. The number 1,450 kWh/y for 120 liters SWH includes the 250 kWh/y electric backup.

SWH in size of 120 liters supplies 1,800 kWh equivalent of hot water per year [1]. At the time of the surveys [2], [3] only 1,200 kWh/y were used and 600 kWh/y was wasted as excessive heat in summer.

Table 48 - Energy demand using 150 liters storage tank, kWh/y [1] [2] [3]

Storage tank	Liters	120	150
Energy demand	kWh/y	1,450	1,813
Electric backup	kWh/y	250	313

Daily demand for energy is not the result of the division of 1,450 kWh/y by 365 days in a year. The demand depends on the storage tank temperature and the city water temperature.

23. Electric Backup

As mentioned above, the electric backup of 150 liters SWH is precisely determined using national statistics based on hundreds of thousands of actual meters' readings every month for many years. The electric backup of 150 liters SWH is 313 kWh per year.

Generally, even on the coldest day of the Israeli winter, there is enough solar energy on the sunny days to heat the SWH to the desired temperature. The backup is required on cloudy days not only in winter but also in spring and autumn. To avoid counting such days every month, the "equivalent storage tank temperature" was set, the storage tank temperature which would require 313 kWh/y backup.

The "equivalent storage tank temperature" is 50.2°C.

Table 49 - Determination of 50.2°C as equivalent storage tank temperature

	SE only °C	Δt to 50.2°C °C	TstB °C	50.2°C backup kWh/d	50.2°C backup kWh/m
January	34.4	15.8	50.2	2.8	86
February	38.1	12.1	50.2	2.1	59
March	44.4	5.8	50.2	1.0	32
April	49.0	1.2	50.2	0.2	7
May	52.9		52.9		0
June	58.6		58.6		0
July	58.8		58.8		0
August	59.9		59.9		0
September	56.4		56.4		0
October	48.9	1.3	50.2	0.2	7
November	42.4	7.8	50.2	1.4	41
December	34.8	15.4	50.2	2.7	83
Σ kWh/y					313

24. Storage Tank Temperature Including Backup

The storage tank electric backup power is 2.5 kW [6]. Maximum demand for backup is 2.8 kWh/day in January. Considering the use of hot water at 19:00, 0.3 kWh should be supplied between 17:00 and 18:00 and 2.5 kWh between 18:00 and 19:00.

Table 50 - Backup contribution to the storage tank temperature

	ELb kWh/d	18:00 kWh/hr	18:00 kcal/hr	18:00 ΔT °C	19:00 kWh/hr	19:00 kcal/hr	19:00 ΔT °C	ΔT/day °C
January	2.8	0.3	224	1.49	2.5	2,150	14.33	15.82
February	2.1				2.1	1,808	12.05	12.05
March	1.0				1.0	875	5.83	5.83
April	0.2				0.2	187	1.24	1.24
May								
June								
July								
August								
September								
October	0.2				0.2	191	1.27	1.27
November	1.4				1.4	1,170	7.80	7.80
December	2.7	0.2	153	1.02	2.5	2,150	14.33	15.35

Table 51 - Storage tank temperature including backup, TstB, °C

hr -->	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19
January	8.0	7.9	7.7	7.9	9.1	11.8	15.5	20.1	25.0	29.7	33.4	35.5	36.4	35.9	36.7	50.2
February	8.7	8.6	8.7	8.9	10.3	13.9	17.7	22.0	26.3	30.8	35.1	37.3	39.4	39.9	39.1	50.2
March	9.4	9.2	9.3	9.8	11.5	14.8	19.2	24.4	30.1	35.7	40.5	44.0	45.9	46.3	45.5	50.2
April	13.7	13.3	13.7	14.8	17.3	21.1	26.0	31.6	37.2	42.7	46.5	49.2	50.7	50.8	50.1	50.2
May	15.1	15.3	16.2	18.0	21.0	25.3	30.5	36.0	41.5	46.5	50.6	53.3	54.6	54.7	54.1	52.9
June	18.4	18.7	19.4	21.1	23.9	27.9	33.0	38.6	44.4	49.8	54.3	57.6	59.6	60.1	59.7	58.6
July	19.9	20.0	20.7	22.0	24.3	27.6	32.4	37.9	43.6	49.1	53.8	57.4	59.6	60.3	59.9	58.8
August	20.3	20.1	20.6	21.7	24.0	27.9	33.0	38.8	45.0	50.5	55.5	59.2	61.3	61.7	61.1	59.9
September	19.0	18.8	19.3	20.7	23.8	28.3	32.9	38.1	44.6	49.6	54.6	57.3	58.3	58.4	57.5	56.4
October	16.5	16.3	16.6	18.0	20.6	25.9	31.3	36.1	40.5	45.4	48.7	50.4	51.2	50.9	49.9	50.2
November	11.5	11.3	11.2	12.5	15.5	19.8	24.8	30.3	35.5	40.0	43.3	45.0	45.0	44.2	43.3	50.2
December	8.5	8.3	8.1	8.4	9.4	12.4	16.7	21.6	26.1	30.3	32.7	36.4	37.0	36.4	36.7	50.2

25. Storage Tank Energy Including Backup

Table 52 - Backup energy, ELb

	ELb kcal/d	ELb kcal/hr
January	2,373	85.6
February	1,808	58.9
March	875	31.5
April	187	6.5
May	0	0.0
June	0	0.0
July	0	0.0
August	0	0.0
September	0	0.0
October	191	6.9
November	1,170	40.8
December	2,303	83.0
Σ		313.2
to SE		11.6%

Table 53 - Storage tank energy including backup, EstB, kcal/day

	Est kcal/d	ELb kcal/d	EstB kcal/d	EstB kWh/m
January	3,486	2,373	5,860	211
February	3,875	1,808	5,683	185
March	4,485	875	5,360	193
April	4,547	187	4,733	165
May	4,807	0	4,807	173
June	5,101	0	5,101	178
July	4,937	0	4,937	178
August	5,032	0	5,032	181
September	4,749	0	4,749	166
October	4,254	191	4,444	160
November	4,093	1,170	5,263	184
December	3,491	2,303	5,794	209
Σ				2,184
to SE				80.8%

26. Water Stratification

Water stratification is a very important feature of solar water heaters. The stratification prevents mixing of all water in the storage tank.

For example, if the stratification is 10°C temperature difference and the temperature on top of the storage tank is 40°C and at the bottom 30°C, mixing all the water in the storage tank will result in average temperature of 35°C, which is useless (too cold) for shower. Therefore it is very important to keep the stratification as high as possible. Vertical storage tanks have much better stratification than horizontal storage tanks. Solar legislation in Israel requires bigger collector for horizontal storage tank [1].

Every opening of a hot water tap at home causes the flow of city water (cold water) to the storage tank, affecting the stratification. The stronger water flow is more harmful to the stratification. On the other hand, slower hot water flow wastes time waiting for the hot water.

The estimation in this work is that 20% of the storage tank hot water will be mixed with cold water resulting in temperature below 37°C in summer, and 40% in winter. This work assumes that the hot water is used only once a day at 19:00.

Table 54 - Mix with cold water at the bottom of the storage tank

	Tc °C	Mixed <37°C	Volume loss Liter
January	15.1	40%	60
February	15.7	39%	58
March	17.2	36%	54
April	20.0	31%	46
May	20.0	31%	46
June	23.4	24%	36
July	25.1	21%	31
August	25.5	20%	30
September	24.6	22%	33
October	21.8	27%	41
November	19.5	31%	47
December	16.1	38%	57
Ave	20.3	30%	45

The mixed layer is from the bottom of the storage tank to the height where the hot water still remains 37°C at the end of the use of the hot water.

Considering 10°C stratification in the storage tank, the water temperature at the bottom of the storage tank is 5°C lower than the storage tank average water temperature. The stratification changes by 1°C with each 10% of the storage tank height.

Following is an example for January.

The average water temperature in the storage tank is 50.2°C. Thanks to the stratification the temperature on the top of the storage tank is 5°C higher, 55.2°C, and on the bottom, 5°C lower, 45.2°C. Before using the hot water, the temperature of the lower edge of the mixed layer is 45.2°C (TmixLow). Considering 40% mixed layer height in January, the temperature of the upper edge of the mixed layer is 4°C higher than the lower edge (1°C per each 10%), 49.2°C (TmixHi).

The average temperature of the mixed layer before the use of the hot water is the average between 45.2°C and 49.2°C, 47.2°C (Tmix).

The energy loss caused by the mixed layer is $(47.2^{\circ}\text{C}-T_c)*60$ Liters of water.

Table 55 - Mixed layer energy losses, Emix, kWh/month

	TmixLow °C	TmixHi °C	Volume loss Liter	Emix kcal/day	Emix kWh/m
January	45.2	49.2	60	240	8.7
February	45.2	49.1	58	226	7.4
March	45.2	48.8	54	195	7.0
April	45.2	48.3	46	140	4.9
May	47.9	51.0	46	140	5.0
June	53.6	56.1	36	87	3.1
July	53.8	55.9	31	64	2.3
August	54.9	56.9	30	60	2.2
September	51.4	53.5	33	71	2.5
October	45.2	47.9	41	110	4.0
November	45.2	48.3	47	148	5.2
December	45.2	49.0	57	217	7.8
Σ					59.9
to SE					2.2%

27. Useful Energy Stored in Storage Tank

$$\text{EstU} = \text{EstB} - \text{Emix}$$

EstU useful energy stored in storage tank
 EstB energy stored in storage tank with backup
 Emix energy loss caused by the mixed layer of the hot water and cold water entering the storage tank, resulting in mixed water temperature below the temperature that can be used for shower (below 37°C)

Table 56 - Useful energy stored in storage tank, EstU

	EstB kcal/d	Emix kcal/d	EstU kcal/d	EstU kWh/y
January	5,860	240	5,620	203
February	5,683	226	5,457	178
March	5,360	195	5,165	186
April	4,733	140	4,593	160
May	4,807	140	4,668	168
June	5,101	87	5,013	175
July	4,937	64	4,873	176
August	5,032	60	4,972	179
September	4,749	71	4,678	163
October	4,444	110	4,334	156
November	5,263	148	5,115	178
December	5,794	217	5,577	201
Σ				2,124
to SE				78.6%

28. Hot Water Flow

Hot water from the storage tank is mixed in the tap with cold water (city water) to get 37°C.

Typical hot water flow for shower head is 5 liters per minute of mixed hot and cold water.

Table 57 - Water flow in shower head

Water flow	0.083	L/s
Water flow	5	liter/minute
Water flow	300	L/hr
Water flow	0.30	m ³ /hr

The water flow is a mix of hot water and cold water resulting in 37°C, the temperature comfortable for shower. The mix depends on the storage tank temperature and the cold water temperature.

The following equations may be used to find the mix ratio:

$$F_c * T_c + F_h * T_h = 5 \text{ [L/min]} * 37^\circ\text{C}$$

$$F_c + F_h = 5 \text{ [L/min]}$$

F_c cold water flow [L/min]
 F_h hot water flow [L/min]
 T_c cold water temperature [°C]
 T_h hot water temperature [°C]

Formula 6 - Hot water mix ratio

$$F_h \text{ [L/min]} = (185 - 5 * T_c) / (T_h - T_c)$$

185 is the result multiplication of 5 [L/min] and 37°C.

T_h is an average between the storage tank temperature and 37°C.

Table 58 - Flow of hot water from the storage tank to the shower

	T _c °C	T _{stB} °C	T _h °C	F _h L/min
January	15.1	50.2	43.6	3.8
February	15.7	50.2	50.2	3.1
March	17.2	50.2	50.2	3.0
April	20.0	50.2	46.9	3.2
May	20.0	52.9	51.6	2.7
June	23.4	58.6	54.4	2.2
July	25.1	58.8	52.9	2.1
August	25.5	59.9	55.8	1.9
September	24.6	56.4	55.4	2.0
October	21.8	50.2	51.5	2.6
November	19.5	50.2	53.0	2.6
December	16.1	50.2	52.8	2.8
Ave	20.3	53.2	51.5	2.7

Table 59 - Duration of hot water flow in shower

	Volume loss Liter	Volume left Liter	Fh L/min	Time sup minutes	Time sup hours
January	60	90	3.8	23	0.39
February	58	92	3.1	30	0.50
March	54	96	3.0	32	0.53
April	46	104	3.2	33	0.55
May	46	104	2.7	39	0.65
June	36	114	2.2	52	0.86
July	31	119	2.1	56	0.93
August	30	120	1.9	63	1.05
September	33	117	2.0	58	0.97
October	41	109	2.6	43	0.71
November	47	103	2.6	39	0.66
December	57	93	2.8	33	0.54
Ave	45	105	2.7	42	0.70

The average time of available hot water for a shower is 42 minutes, minimum 23 minutes in January.

29. Excessive Energy, Solar Energy Not Used

The last month after winter when backup is required is April. It is considered in this work that energy stored in the storage tank above the April level including backup is "excessive energy, solar energy not used".

Table 60 - Excessive energy, solar energy not used, EE

	Time sup minutes	Used	Unused	EstU kcal/d	EE kcal/d	EE kWh/y
January	23	100%	0%	5,620	0	0.0
February	30	100%	0%	5,457	0	0.0
March	32	100%	0%	5,165	0	0.0
April	33	100%	0%	4,593	0	0.0
May	39	85%	15%	4,668	695	25.1
June	52	64%	36%	5,013	1,824	63.6
July	56	59%	41%	4,873	1,985	71.6
August	63	52%	48%	4,972	2,379	85.8
September	58	56%	44%	4,678	2,039	71.2
October	43	77%	23%	4,334	1,001	36.1
November	39	84%	16%	5,115	836	29.2
December	33	100%	0%	5,577	0	0.0
Σ to SE						382.4 14.1%

30. Hot Water Supply Pipe Heat Exchange Energy Losses

Supply pipe is between the storage tank and the bathroom of the apartment. The total pipe length is estimate as 10 m per apartment on average.

Table 61 - Input data for hot water supply pipe to each apartment (Xs)

Parameter	ID	Value	Unit
conductivity of inside laminar layer - water	α_{in}	10,000	kcal/m ² °C,hr
thickness of pipe		2	mm
thickness of pipe	th1	0.002	m
plastic pipe inside diameter		12	mm
plastic pipe inside diameter	din1	0.012	m
plastic pipe outside diameter		16	mm
plastic pipe outside diameter	dout1	0.016	m
specific thermal conductivity of plastic	λ_1	0.301	kcal/m°°C,hr
insulation thickness		13	mm
insulation thickness	th2	0.013	m
insulation inside diameter		16	mm
insulation inside diameter	din2	0.016	m
insulation outside diameter		42	mm
insulation outside diameter	dout2	0.042	m
insulation specific thermal conductivity	λ_2	0.0334	kcal/m°°C,hr
conductivity of outside laminar layer - air	α_{out}	6.61	kcal/m ² °C,hr
pipe length per apartment	L	10	m

Table 62 - UA heat transfer in hot water supply pipe from storage tank to shower (Xs)

Inside laminar layer thermal resistance	$1 / (\alpha_{in} * din1)$	0.0083	M°°C,hr/kcal
Plastic pipe thermal resistance	$LN(dout1/din1) / (2 * \lambda_1)$	0.4780	M°°C,hr/kcal
Insulation thermal resistance	$LN(dout2/din2) / (2 * \lambda_2)$	14.4638	M°°C,hr/kcal
Outside laminar layer thermal resistance	$1 / (\alpha_{out} * dout2)$	3.5998	M°°C,hr/kcal
Total resistance	Σr	18.5498	M°°C,hr/kcal
Pipe length	L	10	m
UA heat transfer per apartment	$UA = \pi * L / \Sigma r$	1.6936	kcal/hr°°C

$$X_s = \Delta t * 1.6936 \text{ kcal/hr}^\circ\text{C}$$

Water temperature in the supply pipe decreases with the use, starting with the maximum storage tank temperature including backup heating (TstB), and ending with the minimum temperature for the shower (37°C).

$$\Delta t = \text{Ave}(T_{stB}, 37^{\circ}\text{C}) - T_b$$

TstB storage tank temperature including backup heating, °C

Tb temperature inside the building

Table 63 - Hot water supply pipe heat exchange energy losses, Xs

	Tb °C	TstB °C	Qsup kcal/hr	Time sup hr/d	Xs kcal/d	Xs kWh/month
January	16.1	50.2	58	0.39	23	0.81
February	16.7	50.2	57	0.50	28	1.01
March	18.2	50.2	54	0.53	29	1.04
April	22.0	50.2	48	0.55	26	0.94
May	24.0	52.9	49	0.55	27	0.97
June	27.4	58.6	53	0.55	29	1.05
July	29.1	58.8	50	0.55	28	1.00
August	29.5	59.9	52	0.55	28	1.02
September	28.6	56.4	47	0.55	26	0.93
October	25.8	50.2	41	0.55	23	0.82
November	20.5	50.2	50	0.55	28	0.99
December	17.1	50.2	56	0.54	30	1.10
Σ						11.69
to SE						0.4%

31. Hot Water Supply Pipe Thermal Mass Energy Losses

Table 64 - Hot water supply pipe thermal mass, MCs, kcal/°C

plastic pipe inside diameter		12	mm
plastic pipe inside diameter	din1	0.012	m
cross-section area	Ain1	0.0001	m ²
plastic pipe outside diameter		16	mm
plastic pipe outside diameter	dout1	0.016	m
cross-section area	Aout1	0.0002	m ²
cross-section area	A1	0.0001	m ²
pipe length	L	10	m
pipe volume	V1	0.001	m ³
plastic density	ρ1	938	kg/m ³
pipe mass	m1	0.8	kg
plastic specific heat	c1	0.55	kcal/kg°C
thermal mass pipe	MC1	0.45	kcal/°C
insulation inside diameter		16	mm
insulation inside diameter	din2	0.016	m
cross-section area	Ain2	0.0002	m ²
insulation outside diameter		42	mm
insulation outside diameter	dout2	0.042	m
cross-section area	Aout2	0.0014	m ²
cross-section area	A2	0.0012	m ²
insulation volume	V2	0.01	m ³
insulation density	ρ2	85	kg/m ³
insulation mass	m2	1.0	kg
insulation specific heat	c2	0.48	kcal/kg°C
insulation thermal mass	MC2	0.48	kcal/°C
water in pipe volume	Ain1*L	0.001	m ³
water density	ρw	1,000	kg/m ³
water in pipe mass	mw	1.1	kg
water specific heat	cw	1.00	kcal/kg°C
water in pipe thermal mass	MCw	1.1	kcal/°C
thermal mass per apartment	MCs	2.1	kcal/°C

The temperature of the water left in the supply pipe after use is 37°C.

$$M_s = \Delta t * MC_s$$

$$\Delta t = 37^\circ\text{C} - T_b$$

$$M_s = (37^\circ\text{C} - T_b) * MC_s$$

M _s	thermal mass energy loss of hot water, kcal/day
MC _s	hot water supply pipe thermal mass, MCs, kcal/°C
T _b	temperature inside the building, °C
37°C	minimum hot water temperature used for shower

Table 65 - Hot water supply pipe thermal mass energy losses, Ms

	Tb °C	Δt °C	Ms kcal/d	Ms kWh/m
January	16.1	20.9	43	1.4
February	16.7	20.3	42	1.5
March	18.2	18.8	39	1.4
April	22.0	15.0	31	1.1
May	24.0	13.0	27	0.9
June	27.4	9.6	20	0.7
July	29.1	7.9	16	0.6
August	29.5	7.5	15	0.5
September	28.6	8.4	17	0.6
October	25.8	11.2	23	0.8
November	20.5	16.5	34	1.2
December	17.1	19.9	41	1.5
Σ				12.3
to SE				0.5%

32. Temperature Drop in Supply Pipe

The hot water flow at 37°C is 5 Liters per minute.

Table 66 - Temperature drop in supply pipe

hot water flow	5	L/m
Tst	37.00	°C
Tb	16.07	°C
Δt	20.93	°C
UA	1.69	kcal/hr°C
Q	35.44	kcal/hr
pipe inside diameter	12	mm
pipe inside diameter	0.012	m
pipe length	10	m
pipe volume	0.0011	m ³
pipe volume	1.13	Liter
flow time	0.23	minutes
flow time	0.0038	hr
energy loss during flow time	0.13	kcal
water temperature drop	0.12	°C
temperature in shower	36.88	°C

The last liter of hot water leaving the storage tank at 37°C reaches the shower at 36.88°C.

33. Energy Used

$$\mathbf{EU = EstU - EE - Xs}$$

$$\text{EstU} = \text{Est} - \text{Emix}$$

$$\mathbf{Est = SE - Xc - Xst - Mc - Msc}$$

Table 67 - Energy used, EU, kWh/month

	EstU	EE	Xs	EU
January	117	0	0.8	116
February	119	0	1.0	118
March	155	0	1.0	154
April	154	0	0.9	153
May	168	25	1.0	142
June	175	64	1.0	110
July	176	72	1.0	103
August	179	86	1.0	92
September	163	71	0.9	91
October	149	34	0.8	114
November	138	22	1.0	114
December	118	0	1.1	117
Σ	1,811	374	11.7	1,425
to SE	67.0%	13.8%	0.4%	52.7%

34. Circulation Pump Energy Consumption

According to the publication [9] the nominal power is 6 Watt for each 150 liters storage tank.

Table 68 - Circulation pump energy consumption per apartment, E_{Lp}

	Sun hours hr/day	E _{Lp} kWh/d	E _{Lp} kWh/month
January	10.3	0.06	1.9
February	11.1	0.07	1.9
March	12.0	0.07	2.2
April	13.0	0.08	2.3
May	13.8	0.08	2.6
June	14.3	0.09	2.6
July	14.1	0.08	2.6
August	13.3	0.08	2.5
September	12.4	0.07	2.2
October	11.4	0.07	2.1
November	10.5	0.06	1.9
December	10.1	0.06	1.9
Σ			26.7

35. Energy Balance of SWH

The balance is for a single apartment.

$$\mathbf{E_{in} = E_{out}}$$

E_{in} total energy input
E_{out} total energy output

35.1. Energy Input

$$\mathbf{E_{in} = SE + ELb + ELp}$$

E_{in} total energy input
SE solar energy leaving collectors for single apartment
ELb energy consumption for electric backup
ELp electricity consumption of circulation pump for one apartment

Table 69 - Energy input, Ein, kWh/month

	SE kWh/m	ELb kWh/m	ELp kWh/m	Ein kWh/m
January	175	86	2	263
February	176	59	2	237
March	233	32	2	267
April	232	7	2	241
May	257	0	3	260
June	263	0	3	265
July	259	0	3	262
August	265	0	2	268
September	243	0	2	245
October	220	7	2	229
November	204	41	2	247
December	174	83	2	259
Σ	2,703	313	27	3,043
to SE	100%	12%	1%	113%
to EU	190%	22%	2%	214%

35.2. Total Heat Exchange Losses

$$\mathbf{XT = Xc + Xst + Xs}$$

XT	total heat exchange losses
Xc	heat exchange losses of circulation pipes
Xst	heat exchange losses of storage tank
Xs	heat exchange losses of hot water supply pipes between the storage tank and the shower

Table 70 - Total heat exchange losses, XT, kWh/month

	Xc	Xst	Xs	XT
January	13	8	1	21
February	13	7	1	22
March	22	10	1	33
April	25	10	1	35
May	29	11	1	41
June	28	11	1	40
July	26	11	1	37
August	27	11	1	39
September	25	10	1	36
October	20	9	1	30
November	19	9	1	29
December	12	7	1	21
Σ	258	115	12	384
to SE	10%	4%	0%	14%
to EU	18%	8%	1%	27%

35.3. Total Thermal Mass Losses

$$\mathbf{MT = Mc + Msc + Ms}$$

MT	total losses in thermal mass
Mc	thermal mass losses of circulation pipes
Mst	thermal mass losses of solar collector
Ms	thermal mass losses of hot water supply pipe

Table 71 - Total thermal mass losses, MT, kWh/month

	Mc	Msc	Ms	MT
January	20	9	1	30
February	21	9	2	31
March	28	11	1	41
April	28	11	1	40
May	32	12	1	45
June	33	13	1	46
July	33	13	1	46
August	34	13	1	47
September	30	12	1	43
October	27	11	1	39
November	23	10	1	35
December	20	9	1	30
Σ	328	131	12	472
to SE	12%	5%	0%	17%
to EU	23%	9%	1%	33%

35.4. Energy Output First Iteration

$$\mathbf{Eout = EU + Emix + XT + MT + EE + ELp}$$

Eout	total energy output
EU	useful energy, energy of hot water actually used for showers
Emix	energy loss caused by the mixed layer of the hot water and cold water entering the storage tank, resulting in mixed water temperature below the temperature that can be used for shower (below 37°C)
XT	total heat exchange losses
MT	total losses in thermal mass
EE	excessive energy, solar energy not used
ELp	electricity consumption of circulation pump for one apartment

Table 72 - Energy output first iteration, Eout, kWh/month

	EU	Emix	XT	MT	EE	ELp	Eout
January	202	9	21	30	0	2	264
February	177	7	22	31	0	2	238
March	185	7	33	41	0	2	268
April	159	5	35	40	0	2	242
May	142	5	41	45	25	3	261
June	110	3	40	46	64	3	266
July	103	2	37	46	72	3	263
August	92	2	39	47	86	2	268
September	91	2	36	43	71	2	246
October	119	4	30	39	36	2	230
November	148	5	29	35	29	2	248
December	200	8	21	30	0	2	260
Σ	1,730	60	384	472	382	27	3,055
to SE	64%	2%	14%	17%	14%	1%	113%
to EU	100%	3%	22%	27%	22%	2%	177%

35.5. Difference Between Energy Input and OutputTable 73 - Difference between energy output and input, ERR, kWh/month

	Ein	Eout	ERR	ERR
January	263	264	+1.4	+0.5%
February	237	238	+1.5	+0.6%
March	267	268	+1.4	+0.5%
April	241	242	+1.1	+0.5%
May	260	261	+0.9	+0.4%
June	265	266	+0.7	+0.3%
July	262	263	+0.6	+0.2%
August	268	268	+0.5	+0.2%
September	245	246	+0.6	+0.3%
October	229	230	+0.8	+0.4%
November	247	248	+1.2	+0.5%
December	259	260	+1.5	+0.6%
Σ	3,043	3,055	12	+0.4%
to SE	113%	113%	0%	
to EU	176%	177%	1%	

ERR calculation error, difference between energy output (Eout) and energy input (Ein)

The first iteration of the balance shows a small difference (0.4%) between input and output of energy. One of the reasons for this calculation error is the conservative approach to the calculations, resulting in overestimation of energy losses. To equalize the balance, the energy output must be reduced by 0.4% on average.

The less accurate estimation is for Emix, energy loss in the mixed layer on the bottom of the storage tank. Therefore, the Emix component of the balance will be reduced in the corrected Eout by the difference between the Eout and Ein.

35.6. Corrected Iteration of Mixed Layer Losses

Table 74 - Corrected iteration of mixed layer losses, Emix, kWh/month

	OLD	ERR	Emix
January	8.7	+1.4	7.2
February	7.4	+1.5	5.8
March	7.0	+1.4	5.7
April	4.9	+1.1	3.8
May	5.0	+0.9	4.1
June	3.1	+0.7	2.3
July	2.3	+0.6	1.7
August	2.2	+0.5	1.6
September	2.5	+0.6	1.8
October	4.0	+0.8	3.2
November	5.2	+1.2	3.9
December	7.8	+1.5	6.4
Σ	59.9	12.3	47.6
to SE	2.2%	0.5%	1.8%
to EU	3.5%	0.7%	2.8%

35.7. Corrected Energy Output

Table 75 - Corrected energy output, kWh/month

	EU	Emix	XT	MT	EE	ELp	Eout
January	202	7.2	21	30	0	2	263
February	177	5.8	22	31	0	2	237
March	185	5.7	33	41	0	2	267
April	159	3.8	35	40	0	2	241
May	142	4.1	41	45	25	3	260
June	110	2.3	40	46	64	3	265
July	103	1.7	37	46	72	3	262
August	92	1.6	39	47	86	2	268
September	91	1.8	36	43	71	2	245
October	119	3.2	30	39	36	2	229
November	148	3.9	29	35	29	2	247
December	200	6.4	21	30	0	2	259
Σ	1,730	48	384	472	382	27	3,043
to SE	64%	2%	14%	17%	14%	1%	113%
to EU	100%	3%	22%	27%	22%	2%	176%

Table 76 - Main components of energy output

		kWh/y	to SE	to Ein
Energy used	EU	1,730	64%	57%
Energy loses	XT+MT	856	32%	28%
Mixed layer losses	Emix	48	2%	2%
Circulation pump	ELp	27	1%	1%
Excessive SE	EE	382	14%	13%
Σ		3,043	113%	100%

35.8. Energy Input and Output

Table 77 - Energy input and output

		In	Out
Circulation pump	ELp	27	27
Excessive SE	EE		382
Energy used	EU		1,730
Heat Exchange losses	XT		384
Thermal Mass losses	MT		472
Mixed layer losses	Emix		48
Backup	ELb	313	
Solar Energy from collectors	SE	2,703	
Σ		3,043	3,043

Chart 3 - Energy balance, kWh/y

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